

DIGITAL COMPETENCY AND RAMP UP COVID-19 FIGHTING: A BANGLADESHI YOUTH PERSPECTIVES

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Introduction:

While many developed nations like United States of America (USA), United Kingdom (UK), Italy, Spain and other European countries face challenges associated with Covid-19, the situation in most developing countries like Bangladesh is opposite. Though, Bangladesh is also included as the high risk nations of Covid-19 that has first discovered in the Chinese city Wuhan since December, 2019 (Haque et al., 2020). The velocities of young population in developing nations are very high. Bangladesh had a presitigious history of the youth contribution during the freedom fight happened in 1971 under the guidance and great leadership of the Father of the nation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman. However, during the Covid-19 pandemic situation where the social distancing is the vital to lead the normal life, then how does the Bangladeshi youth take pivotal role to combat the Covid-19 circumstances? The study will be addressed this important question and identified appropriate remedies by applying new skills and talents that is called Digital Competencies (DC). Modern digital technologies especially Information Communication Technologies (ICT) are the catalyst of societal changes. So, the knowledge and skills that enables the youth to operate the digital technologies for studying, understanding and finding solutions to the current and real problems are ideal concept of digital competency (Kuzminska, Mazorchuk, Morze, Pavlenko, & Prokhorov, 2018). Specifically, the study will be investigated the exploring of Social Media (SM) /Apps by Bangladeshi youth and acquired necessary skills to become an expert performer.

Background of the study:

Population is an all-time hot issue for Bangladesh. Youth are really frontier soldiers worldwide. The UNFPA report 2014 that 1.8 billion youthful manpower who are 10 to 24 aged group, ready to respond to the global crisis (Abusaleh, 2017). According to the Bangladesh population and family census 2011, almost 50 million Bangladeshi youth are moving forward to contribute to the nation (Moum, 2017). Youth are the backbone of national development and they are the real heroes to combat any unsung problems like Covid-19.

On the other hand, digital technologies such as ICT, New Media, Web Casting and 21st century technologies are the booming technology worldwide. As a result, digital literature, behavior and knowledge are important in the recent times. Moreover, youth and technologies are two sides of the global map (Cortesi et al., 2015). ICT backed technologies are multitasking problem solving technologies that enable youth to prepare them for contributing impactful actions. Being a citizen of a developing nation like Bangladesh, the youth need to hunt such a quality that is cheap, easy learning, handy, appropriate and updated (Ala-Mutka, Punie, & Redecker, 2008). Digital competencies/skills are the same quality that is friendly, communicative, sense of initiative and easy learning. It is also ideal for Bangladeshi youth to explore and prepare against global threat like Corona pandemic. Though, Social Media is accessible by the all aged group, DCs are ways of thinking, working and living tools for not only global youth but also Bangladeshi netizens.

Justification of the study:

Bangladesh is a small South Asian country with a very large population and many opportunities. It is also the most densely populated country in the world. Dhaka, at the center of the country, is the capital. Interestingly, all modern ICTs, technologies, social media and applications are available that are shaping a new wave in Bangladeshi's lifestyle. Members of the younger generation (the youth of Bangladesh) are the primary users of social media. Recent studies showed that Bangladesh is one of the leading countries where maximum youth used social media. The study concluded with specific data as Facebook users (88%). It followed YouTube (81%) and IMO (45%) respectively (Prodhan, Islam, & Hossain, 2020). This study will be examined social media use skills among Bangladeshi youth and how they navigate it to fight corona situation. In addition, the study will also be investigated whether DCs influence the search for new knowledge and skills that enhance the qualities of capacity building and enabling young people to deal with some of the prime risks like Covid-19 pandemic.

They are the real heroes of which society dreams, not only in their own country but also worldwide. Three Western scholars have framed the age of youth in a very innovative way (Donald, Anderson, & Spry, 2010). The eyes and minds of youth are always awesome for finding new solutions through their creativity and the power of their imagination (Alves, 2011). When they are full of prospects and futuristic, they turn themselves into a societal asset.

Bangladeshi youth are enthusiastic, grabbing new technologies that they come across, such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter. Today's youth are the future nation builders, with golden prosperous lives waiting for them. They are the real heroes in re-building the nation in accordance with the available resources and with optimism. The youth of Bangladesh have a long history of quickly grabbing new opportunities and promptly providing feedback. A great example is the history of Bangladesh's independence in 1971. The young people at the time had no relevant skills and no training to fight against well-organized forces, but they acquired the relevant training directed by Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman. The result was that, after nine months of struggle, they won the war and established the new country of Bangladesh. The British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) and other international news agencies reported the massive youth contribution. Members of the younger generation are the dreamers who swiftly learn and acquire knowledge. This learning velocity is now even more rapid with technology, including social media, at the forefront. They are also ready to fight another war against Covid-19 by applying the knowledge and skills as DCs describes.

Literature Review:

Social media is a souvenir to the youth. It enables and enlightens them to contribute for the society and the humanity. More advanced way, ICT backed media is counting as a mirror of latest trend of current youth's motivation. It is helping Bangladeshi youth to keep things in control. Being a web based tool, social media is equipping and digitizing the youth community in engaging various activities even to fight against national disaster like corona pandemic.

Youths are Yolk: Youth are the symbol of power and prosperity in every society. They are the only force to sacrifice for humanity. Youth are the natural agent of modernity and new technology adaptive group (Sukarieh & Tannock, 2014). They are also such people who have the capacity to transform the worst of everything to make wonderful to the earth. Youth have the adaptive ability to think modern fashion and styles. Youth are reshaping the society in every single minute

throughout the globe. They are really the symbol of imagination, creativity, positive and socio-economic changer (Donald et al., 2010). The future belongs to the young. They live on hope and turn into the future leader. They can plan, act and demonstrate all aspects of development, which are needful to the society particularly where they live. Youth are the pillar to understand social need (Park, Kim, & Cho, 2008). . Moreover, youth are the lifeblood of any nation. They have confidence and hard working manner that lead to gear up the society. Social media is sliding this gear up mission by connecting the technology and the youth spirit. New media technology always attracts the audience by their age and education (Nick, Andreas, & Friedrich, 2010).

Digital Dogma: Youth are growing with digital myth. They cannot live without digital devices. Four things are outstanding for daily lives of today's youth such as (a) computer (b) internet (c) video game and (d) mobile phones (Subrahmanyam & Smahel, 2010). They prefer to live with modern environment where their communicative desires are available. Truly, young generation are in the forefront of every social, economic and political movement (Lyngdoh, 2005). That is why the youth are the premeiur stakeholders of latest gadjets. Operating and performing ICT backed media confident young generation to cope up the situation which is the key competencies for lifelong learnings (Union, 2010). 21st century is the milestone of digital era where lives, goods, machines and other surromdings are moving with digital spirit. Even, the day to day performances are happening through digital tools like touch screen (Neumann, Finger, & Neumann, 2017). It is always wise to slove critical issues with critical thinking. Young generation and ICT backed social media are equivalent in terms of enermous power. Both are the vital player to confirm the changes in any situation. This is the pick time to connect a harmonious bonding between the youth and social media. It is also required to tackle any unexpected situation like corona pandemic. The study will focus and investgate that relational package called digital competency that is out of discussion of the previous research works.

Corana Combating: Almost every nation in the global map has already touched by the novel corona virus spreading first from the Chinese city Wuhan since December 2019. Bangladesh that is one of the most densely populated countries in the South Asian region has also threatened by covid-19 that known as a new respiratory virus since February 2020. Young Bangladesh Open University teacher Al-Amin Sarker has already researched on the life standard of Bangladeshi people. He found that northern territory of Bangladesh especially Rangpur area are leading most

vulnerable lives during the Covid-19 pandemic (Mondal et al., 2020). Being a global crisis, Bangladesh is also under threat of long-term corona crisis. They need to know the short way, which involves less financial involvement to combat with corona such as of acquiring knowledge for changing attitude on daily practice to address pandemic risks (Haque et al., 2020). Being a netizen of digital era we need to hunt new techniques to utilize ICT backed media for fighting against Covid-19. The proposed study will take those responsibilities through its real investigation.

Research Questions (RQ):

Research Question always boost up to summaries statement of the problem (McCaslin & Scott, 2003). It is the first step to frame the main research problem. It is also the ideal way to reply the problem and generate new knowledge (Wood & Ross-Kerr, 2010). RQ is using as a core option to level the main research problem in qualitative research. It is also useful tool for early career researchers. Remembering the above mentioned introduction, it was intended to frame the tailored research problem, the following three research questions set to the proposed research:

RQ1: What are the digital competencies of Bangladeshi youth to use ICT backed social media/apps such as Facebook, Youtube, Zoom and Skype?

RQ2: Do the Social media/apps usage open any role-playing knowledge for Bangladeshi youth?

RQ3: Does the achieved knowledge enable youth to engage to address life-threatening disaster in Bangladesh like Covid-19?

Research Objectives (RO):

To identify widely used Digital / ICT backed media by youth Bangladeshi

- To draw youth intention to explore social media
- To prepare a guide for operating social media/apps for contributing to national needs while exploring digital devices and
- To encourage youth to combat Covid-19 by bonding with digital practices

Research Methodology:

As a Qualitative research, extensive documents of scholarly journals & articles, research reports, books, government statements and websites with relevant topics to explore ICT backed social media interaction by Bangladeshi youth have used to search the answer of the research questions. Furthermore, a survey has also conducted to examine digital media operation techniques by youth in keeping mind of combating Covid-19 by applying effective digital competencies. It has chosen for three reasons. First, it is obvious that complex phenomena such as social media used by major population group (youth) and acquired digital skills that lead to contribute emergency needs. In this situation, it is easiest to generate quantitative results based on data (Sampson Jr et al., 2014). Second reason is the involvement of large study group from different locations, and third, is the cheap cost and easy to carry on the tasks. Based on the above analysis, it has investigated the selected social media (Facebook, Youtube, Zoom and Skype) usage that has focused in Bangladeshi youth.

A.Study Area: Dhaka is the capital city of Bangladesh. It is also a metropoliton city. Total area of this city is 306.4 km² and the population size is 21006000 as of 2020.

B.Specific Study Method: Overall, two specific methods have been employed to investigate digital competencies of Bangladeshi youth:

1. Survey with ask questions for using top raked social media
2. Survey with questions for requesting self-assement skills and

C.Study Population: Being a study focusing young people, the Bangladeshi youth (male/female) between 15 to 29 years have counted as a study population. According to the last national census of Bangladesh (2011), 26.3 percent are youth people whose age group are 15 to 30 years old (Graner, Yasmin, & Aziz, 2012).

D.Sampling: The study analyzed 200 youth male and female's using and learning skills of selected social media where the maximum youth belong to the age group of 20-24 years old.

E.Data Collection Method: Being a qualitative study, a moderate survey questionnaire has been designed and applied for collecting realistic data as a whole.

F.Data Analysis Plan: The following two tier analysis pathways have been used to reveal the study's actual results. These are listed as follows:

- Statistical tools for data analysis
- Chi-square test will be confirmed to determine whether a significant relationship exists between two nominal (categorical) variables.

Theoretical Framework:

The Digital Bloom's Taxonomy theory has been followed to elaborate the proposed theory of the study. The Pennsylvanian Benjamin S. Bloom introduced the Bloom theory to the global audience in the 1950's by highlighting taxonomy features of skills in a pyramid structure describing evaluation, synthesis, analysis, application, understanding and knowledge. This theory was not enough to adjust the demand of 80's and 90's. Updated version was required by the massive. As a result the changing version introduced in the 1990's by replacing "create" instead of "evaluation" at the top of the pyramid and dropped the synthesis. This version has drawn the pyramids listing of create, evaluate, analyze, apply, understand and remember. Andrew Churches re-constructed the Bloom's Taxonomy theory to meet the demand of digital age in 2008. He integrated verbs and tasks to address the digital age. He also renamed the theory as "Bloom's Digital Taxonomy theory". The pyramid of bloom's digital theory finally stands as follows:

Figure 1: Bloom's Taxonomy theory

Andrew defined the digital skills into two specific points as verbs and activities which mentioned in the following table.

VERBS	ACTIVITIES
Create	blog, film, integrate, podcast, program, publish
Evaluate	comment, editorialize, moderate, network, post
Analyze	attribute, deconstruct, illustrate, mash, mind map
Apply	chart, display, execute, present, upload
Understand	annotate, Boolean search, journal, tweet
Remember	bookmark, google, link, search

Table 1: Verbs and Activities of Bloom's theory

The Bloom's theory has started the thinking skills to solve the problem in connecting latest digital domain, networks and verbs. Time is moving very fast and technology is spreading very quickly. It is demanding appeal a new conceptual framework which deals the digital media directly. To meet the need, the study has proposed the following pyramid is addressing the digital media especially social media effectively. This framework also describes the digital exploring area and competencies of youth users clearly.

Figure 2: Proposed Conceptual Framework according to the Bloom's theory

The new framework directly address and narrate digital area and competencies that are allowing youth and adolescent for contributing need based actions like Covid-19 pandemic situation. The framework has been considered the following area and competencies:

AREA	COMPETENCIES
1. Attention	1.1 Preparation to access available social media 1.2 Motivation to explore specific social media
2. Information	2.1 Browsing and searching information 2.2 Grabing and Managing information
3. Communication	3.1 Interacting and Sharing through digital technologies 3.2 Engaging and Networking through social media
4. Content Creation	4.1 Developing digital Content 4.2 Content Creation for contribution
5. Safety	5.1 Well being practices 5.2 Protecting personal safety
6. Problem Solving	6.1 Creativity to solve the problem 6.2 Solving problem through digital technologies

Table 2: Area and Competencies of proposed theory

However, the proposed digital competency theory is updated and appropriate to the netizen who are the real digital player interested to contribute to the nation at the emergency moment like Covid-19 situation.

Results and Description:

Youth are vital for every society even the nomad community. Bangladeshi youth are change maker to introduce new technologies to the society. Male and female both have enormous potentialities to explore new media and gain knowledge for serving community and national interest. The following tables and figures are describing details study results with correlation.

Digital Device Using Pattern		Gender-male or female			Total
		Male	Female	Not interested to share	
Digital Device Using Pattern	Always	53	18	9	80
	Most of the time	43	16	7	66
	Sometimes	15	15	1	31
	Often	15	3	5	23
Total		126	52	22	200

Table 3: Genderwise digital device using pattern

Being a moderate Muslim country, the above table shows that 63% male (126) and 26% female (52) somehow use the social media in the time slot of “Always”, “Most of the time”,

“Sometimes”, and “Often”. A total of 11% male and female youth (22) are not interested to share their social media using pattern.

English is the major operating language of Facebook, Youtube, Zoom and Skype. Now, Bengali version is also available. As a result, both the educated with the knowledge of English and people with somewhat knowledge of Bengali are exploring social media in Bangladesh.

		Educational status				Total
		No education	Completed school level/equivalent	Higher Secondary school/equivalent	Graduation/above	
Age in years	10-14 Year	0	20	7	0	27
	15-19 Year	0	3	22	0	25
	20-24 Year	1	9	31	50	91
	25-29 Year	1	4	13	39	57
Total		2	36	73	89	200

Table 3: Respondent's educational status

The table 3 describes that highest numbers of youth (89) are higher educated. Only two youth have no education considered to the survey. Interestingly, the age group of 20-24 is prime force who has quite educational background to operate the digital technologies.

In connection with table-3, the educational background helps the youth to access social media in a wider perspective. The following table-4 shows the details. Total 66% (132) youth are using Facebook as their first preference. Youtube is the second position of choice to the youth who like it most. Nominal numbers of users (only 4) prefer zoom as their first preference.

		First preference to social media			Total
		Facebook	Youtube	Zoom	
Age in years	10-14 Year	23	4	0	27
	15-19 Year	16	8	1	25
	20-24 Year	56	32	3	91
	25-29 Year	37	20	0	57
Total		132	64	4	200

Table 4: First preference of using social media

How the youth define and understand the Digital Competency was the vital question in the study? The following table revealed it specifically.

		Device frequently use to explore ICT baked social media				Total
		Laptop	Smart Phone	Tablet	Other Gadget	
Understanding on Digital Competency	Potentiality to search and access internet-based services	4	15	0	1	20
	Ability to process and use acquired information to address societal critical situation like COVID-19	8	28	2	3	41
	Capacity to utilize digital technologies for supporting critical thinking, creativity and innovation	10	29	0	7	46
	All of the above three	17	57	5	14	93
Total		39	129	7	25	200

Table 5: Understanding of Digital Competency

The highest number of respondents opined that online searching potentiality, ability to hunt required information that are really needed and capacity to utilize digital technologies for supporting innovation are the real frame of Digital Competencies. Digital competency does not necessarily mean only one aspect related to social media. Current study has proved that digital competency includes potentiality, ability and capacity regarding social media usage. Moreover, maximum youth are using smart phones to explore their preferred social media for acquiring knowledge and digital skills.

Respondents are using multiple apps to solve the needbase solution during the Covid situation. The following table-6 narrates it clearly.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	.5	.5	.5
	Disagree	8	4.0	4.0	4.5
	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	37	18.5	18.5	23.0
	Agree	79	39.5	39.5	62.5
	Strongly Agree	75	37.5	37.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: Using of multiple apps to solve problems

Youth contribution level during Covid-19 situation in terms of digital competencies such as disseminating health messages, amplifying awareness voices, and sharing information on Intensive Care

Unit (ICU) or general beds for Covid patient have also examined during the study. The table-7 describes all the issues very smoothly.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very difficult	9	4.5	4.5	4.5
	Difficult	24	12.0	12.0	16.5
	Hesitate	32	16.0	16.0	32.5
	Comfort	79	39.5	39.5	72.0
	Very comfort	56	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 7: Youth Competency level to address covid crisis

The knowledge and skills gained by exploring Digital / ICT –backed technologies enable youth to hunt new data for supporting Covid patients are very important. The youth social media users are vibrant to access networks and combat the situation like current pandemic. Most of the respondent’s strongly agree to perform the relevant activities. The following figure-3 is the right witness.

Figure-3: Level of Preference on exploring Digital or ICT backed technologies

Bangladesh is not a first world country. The health system is not sufficient to tackle Covid-19 situation smartly. It has remarkable shortage on doctors, nurses, hospitals and medicines. But Bangladeshi youth came forward to uplift the healthy Bangladesh during the Covid waves through gaining knowledge from social media exploration and utilizing it at the right place to the right people and on the right time. The following figure-4 shows in details.

Figure 4: Respondents comfortabilities to response through Facebook, Youtube, Zoom and Skype

The above analysis reveals that the social media/apps are used to linking or creating digital content, strengthening, browsing, searching and sharing data, creating awareness etc. Most of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed in this regard. Moreover, the respondents felt either comfort or very comfort to disseminate knowledge, amplifying health messages, supporting patients, maintaining networks, sharing information and discarding fake news regarding COVID-19 through the social media. So, the social media or apps undoubtedly play as a vast vista for knowledge gathering and disseminating by and for the Bangladeshi youth.

Significant Analysis:

Goodman and Kruskal's gamma analysis have been conducted. Additionally, Chi Square test has also conducted to reveal the realistic study output and authentic result.

		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.105	.107	-.980	.327
N of Valid Cases		200			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

Table 8: Symmetric Measures of Linking to create or develop digital content and dissemination knowledge on Covid-19 such as social distancing, hand washing, sanitizing etc.

Goodman and Kruskal's gamma is presented in Table-5 where the "Value" of gamma column is -.105. This indicates that as linking to create or develop digital content is developed, Disseminating Knowledge on COVID-19 such as social distancing, hand washing, sanitizer etc. is not always developed. That means digital content creations through social media exist in the youth groups, but not always for only the dissemination of public knowledge regarding social distance, washing hands or sanitizing etc. The Approximate Significance shows that the statistical significance value (i.e., p-value) is .327, which means $p > .0005$. Therefore, the association between the two is not statistically significant

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	56.292 ^a	12	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 8 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .32.

Table 9: Chi Square Test between collecting information through social media and supporting Covid-19 patient

The above table-9 shows that the p-value < 0.05 indicates that there exists significant relation between sharing data through social media and supporting the COVID-19 patient for different reasons such as ICU beds, plasma donors, oxygen cylinders, ambulances and online consultations. This proves that the achieved knowledge through the social media enables youth to engage or support to address life-threatening disaster like COVID-19 in Bangladesh

The present study centres on the expanded area of Bloom's Taxonomy theory and materializes the attention, information, communication, content creation, safety and problem solving. It reveals who the real attentive social media users, which age groups with what educational status gather information and communicate through the created digital content for the better safety of the communities and how they solve the problem like COVID-19.

Finally, the Goodman and Kruskal's gamma analysis did not find any association between content creation and dissemination of information, but Chi Square test has proved the significance between social media and supporting COVID-19 patients resulting that reflexed the study's outcomes and objectives.

Limitations of the study:

Language and location are the prime limitations of the study. English is the leading language to operate popular social media in Bangladesh such as Facebook, Youtube, Zoom and Skype. Even, the survey questionnaire has also been designed in English whereas respondents are Bengali native. At the same time, it has only considered the capital city Dhaka. Rest of 63 cities of Bangladesh did not consider for further studies. Shortage of sufficient interpreters was another limitation of the study.

Policy Directions:

There are no effective social media operational motivations to the young Bangladeshies. They just connect wifi or data and visit several social media sites. But, the study has revealed three specific issues that will navigate future social media and youth policy framework. Those are as follows:

- a. Enriching the device operation: After attending the study survey session and understanding the imposed latent issues, respondents have realized their motivation to operate the device effectively.
- b. Boosting up the youth productivity: Youth are now alert enough to acquire knowledge and skills from social media interaction. They discovered how to grab information and utilize to address emergency situation such as content creation to support covid patients.
- c. Encouraging to be a digital data entrepreneur: Youth has realized the proverb "Information is powerful than gun power" by searching, disseminating, sharing and

exchanging all relevant data that directly helped national health safety. Many of Bangladeshi youth may be established themselves to be a digital data entrepreneur in near future after getting the message from the study.

Conclusion:

Digital technologies especially social media has no boundary. It has already opened numerous opportunities to the globe. Now a days, it is the global property. Social media not only empower and engage the audiences, it also introduce efficient and appropriate communication channel (Rutsaert et al., 2014). Youth are the prime stakeholders of it and they are leading to reveal new way of pivotal role playing contributions for the betterment in various aspects.

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Appendix-1 : Survey Questionnaire

Digital Competency Survey

Explanation

Three young Bangladeshi social scientists are conducting a survey of digital competency and ramp up covid-19 fighting: A Bangladeshi youth perspective. All feedback will be kept confidential and not used any other purposes except research activities.

The survey will take short time (5 to 10 minutes) to complete. If you have any questions or queries, please feel free to contact Md Abdur Razzak, PhD, at abdurrazzak7545@gmail.com.

1. Are you using any digital device?
 - Yes
 - No
 - partially used (used after long break)
 - I was before, but am not currently user
2. If you answered “YES” to the above question 1, what is your using pattern?
 - Always
 - Most of the time
 - Sometimes
 - Often
3. Which age group identifies you accurately?
 - 10 – 14
 - 15 – 19
 - 20 – 24
 - 25- 29
4. How do you define your gender?
 - Male
 - Female
 - Third gender
 - not interested to share
5. What is your educational status?
 - No education
 - Completed school level/equivalent
 - Higher secondary school/equivalent
 - Graduation/above
6. Which social media is your first preference to use mostly?
 - Facebook
 - Youtube
 - Zoom
 - Skype
7. Which social media is your second choice to use?
 - Facebook
 - Youtube
 - Zoom
 - Skype
8. Which social media is your third choice?
 - Facebook
 - Youtube
 - Zoom
 - Skype
9. Which social media do you engage in the lowest level?

- Facebook ● Youtube ● Zoom ● Skype

10. What is your understanding on “DIGITAL COMPETENCY”?

- Potentiality to search and access internet based services
- Ability to process and use aquired information to address societal critical situation like Covid-19
- Capacity to utilige digital technologies for supporting critical thinking, creativity and innovation
- All of the above three

11. Please rate your level of acceptance on “Exploring Digital/ICT backed technologies-----”?

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Linking to create or develop digital content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strengthening Browsing & Searching Data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sharing Data through ICT backed media	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using multiple aps for need base solutions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creating e-awareness sense of mind to address various problem	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Learning for sustaing effort	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Utiliging option of innovative thinking to address current disasters	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. How comfort to response the followings through Facebook, Youtube, Zoom and Skype?

Please specify your position as “very difficult”, “Difficult”, “Hesitate”, “Comfort”, and “Very Comfort”.

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Hesitate	Comfort	Very Comfort
Disseminating knowledge on Covid-19 such as social distancing, hand washing, sanitizer etc	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amplifying public health messages for example wearing face masks, staying at home, avoiding close contact and more	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supporting Covid patient such as searching ICU beds,	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

plasma donors, oxygen cylinders, ambulances and online consultations					
Coordinating networks like testing stations, Hospital beds, tiffin services and donors	<input type="radio"/>				
Sharing information on medicine, safety at home and relief supports	<input type="radio"/>				
Discarding fake news about Covid syndrome, affected areas, deadbodies and remedies	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Please verify your above actions by clicking “**Yes**” or “**No**”

Self Varification	YES	NO	Not Sure
Do your action T ruthful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does it really H elpful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does it I nspire?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is it N ecessary?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is it K ind?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. Which device you frequently use to explore ICT baked social media?

- Laptop
- Smart mobile
- Tablet
- other gadget

Thank you very much for your kind response. If you have any querries, please contact at Md Abdur Razzak, PhD abdurrazzak7545@gmail.com